

DEVELOPMENT OF A 4-BIT FLASH ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL CONVERTER USING CMOS VLSI 180nm FULL CUSTOM TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract – Analog to digital converters are widely used in all kinds of areas since they can ensure a communication between the computer and the external world, the development of a 4-bit A/D flash type converter as the main objective for this article follows the same purpose. The paper was planned in a way that, with a great number of tables and graphs, most people would be able to understand and replicate the desired results correctly. The simulation, which is the main part of the development of the article, was done using a software called LTSpice, a program with several tools and components that made possible to assemble a converter, besides that, the software also has a tool that allows to create new components, in which it was developed full custom AND and OR logic gates based on CMOS technology. At last, the results show satisfactory graphs that prove the functioning of the converter.

Keywords: A/D Converter; LTSpice; CMOS; *Full Custom*; 4 bits;

INTRODUCTION

Most magnitudes in nature are analog, therefore, to enable the processing of these signals in digital systems, it is necessary to use an analog-to-digital (A/D) converter [1]. Many types of analog signals are present in nature, among them, some examples that can be cited are: temperature, humidity, pressure, audio signals, light intensity and others [2].

A A/D converter, also known as ADC (Analog-to-Digital Converter), consists on a circuit that receives an alternating voltage signal at the input and, after a certain time, it converts that signal into a digital corresponding binary code [2],[3]. Several areas use these types of converters in their equipment, some examples would be the instrumentation area (which uses it for oscilloscopes, digital multimeters, spectrum analyzers and more), the telecommunications area (that uses it for terrestrial communication or satellite communication), communication systems (such as cell phones), medical examinations (by image, radars and others) and many more fields [2], [3], [4].

There are many types of circuits that can perform the conversion of an analog signal into a digital binary code, each one of them with their own advantages and disadvantages. Between those circuits, can be cited:

- Digital ramp ADC;
- Dual ramp ADC;
- Successive approximation ADC;
- Flash ADC (also known as parallel topology ADC);

Knowing the importance of these converters, this work presents the development and simulation of a 4-bit flash analog-to-digital converter using the software LTSpice. Although many comparators are needed to build this circuit (in this case, 15 analog comparators), this topology was chosen for having a higher ADC conversion speed [2].

DEVELOPMENT

For the development of this project, the researchers chose the simulation software called LTSpice, in which it was used the components of the foundry CMOS Mosis Wafer Electrical Foundry IBM

7WL_4LM_ML_HK 180 nm together with the library of CMOS logic gates and the libraries developed by the authors. Fig. 1 represents the architecture of a flash converter N bits.

Figure 1: Structure of an N-bit flash converter [5].

The operations realized in this converter can be divided in three steps: tension division (responsible to create reference tensions), comparison and codification. In the first step, a reference tension (in this case, something around 10V) on a tension divisor that will generate 15 levels of tension (each one with a 0,34V tension).

On the second step, each one of the reference tensions are connected to the inverter port of a operational amplifier (AD549), which will play the role on comparing these reference voltages with an analog voltage (in this case, a 15kHz sine wave that has an amplitude of 2.9V and a DC value of 6.5V). When the value of this sine wave is greater than the reference voltage, the op-amp output will be on high

logic level (approximately 8.5V), otherwise the output will be on low logic level (approximately 0V).

After the comparison, the output signals of each operational amplifiers will go through a priority encoder, which aims to transform this signal into its binary counterpart. To perform this conversion, AND and OR logic gates developed with VLSI full custom technology were used.

On developing the priority encoder, it is initially necessary to associate each one of the OPAMPs outputs possibilities to various AND gates, generating

all 16 possible outcomes. This can be seen in Table 1, where, using “1” as high logic level and “0” as low logic level, it is possible to check the relation between the logic levels of the comparators and the AND gates outputs in each case (excluding Output 16, or “S16”, because it is a logic gate that only will provide a high logic level when all comparators are at a low logic level).

C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10	S11	S12	S13	S14	S15
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

Table 1: Relation between the output of OP AMPs and the inputs of AND gates.

In order to build a 15-input AND gate, it was initially necessary to build a CMOS circuit to a NAND gate, which consists of a pullup network composed of 15 PMOS transistors connected in series and a pull-down network composed of 15 NMOS transistors connected in parallel. when all inputs are at low logic level, all PMOS transistors will start to conduct, in that way, the port output will be 1 and, if any of the 15 inputs becomes high logic level, the gate output will

be 0. Now, to obtain an AND gate, it is necessary connect the NAND gate output to an inverter, which consists of a pull-up network composed of a PMOS transistor and a composite pull-down network composed by a NMOS transistor. To build all AND gates it was required a total of 512 transistors. The Figure 2 shows the developed logic gate circuit.

Figure 2: AND gate CMOS circuit.

relation, along with all possibilities can be verified in Table 2.

The developed component features a time rise and a time fall of approximately 33 ns. In addition to that, the developed component also presents a current of operation of 3mA for a 1 kΩ load.

After the coding stage, it is necessary to transform each one of the AND gates outputs into its binary counterpart. For this, it was used OR logic gates, which will only provide a high logic level when one of its inputs also provides a high logical level. This

S15	S14	S13	S12	S11	S10	S9	S8	S7	S6	S5	S4	S3	S2	S1	D0	D1	D2	D3
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1

Table 2: Relation between AND gate outputs and OR gate outputs.

For the development of an 8-input OR gate, it was initially necessary to develop a NOR gate. For this, a pull-up network composed of 8 PMOS transistors were connected in series and a pull-down network consisting of 8 connected NMOS transistors were connected in parallel. When all entries are in low logic level, all the PMOS transistors will start to conduct, in that way, the output from the gate is at high logic level

“1”. But when one of the inputs is at a high logic level, the transistors NMOS will start to conduct, and then the output of the gate will be at low logical level “0”. In order to obtain a OR gate, it is necessary to connect the output of the NOR gate to an inverter. To build all the OR gates it was necessary a total of 72 transistors (totaling 584 transistors for building all logical gates). Figure 3 shows the developed logic gate circuit.

Figure 3: OR gate CMOS circuit.

The developed component features a time rise and a time fall of approximately 5.5 ns. In addition, the developed component also presents a current of operation of 3 mA for a 1 k Ω load.

After the simulation was done, it was possible to obtain the graphs containing the voltage levels generated in the voltage divider, and the output of operational amplifiers. Fig. 4 show these results obtained in the simulation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4: Relação entre tensão de entrada e saída dos AMPOPs.

As can be observed in Fig. 4, the voltage step generated in the voltage dividers is approximately 0.34V, which means that, in order to change the digital output of the converter, it is necessary to change by 0.34V the analog input voltage. With that, it is possible to observe that as the analog voltage increases, more operational amplifiers have the output at a high logic level, reaching a point where the input voltage becomes greater than the output voltage on the highest reference tension, making all OPAMPs outputs high logic level. However, as the analog voltage starts to decrease, the OPAMPs outputs start to become low logic level, until the analog voltage becomes lower

than the lowest reference tension, causing all OPAMPs outputs to become low logic level.

With this data, it was possible to obtain the digital output of the proposed converter. The Fig. 5 presents the relationship between analog input voltage and output converter digital.

Figure 5: converter digital output.

Following the graphs in Fig. 5 it was possible to obtain the values in Table 3, which show the relation between the voltage ranges at the input of the converter with its digital output. It is worth noting that D0 is the most significant bit.

Tensão de entrada (V)	D0	D1	D2	D3
3,60 – 4,14	0	0	0	0
4,14 – 4,48	0	0	0	1
4,48 – 4,82	0	0	1	0
4,82 – 5,16	0	0	1	1
5,16 – 5,50	0	1	0	0
5,50 – 5,84	0	1	0	1
5,84 – 6,18	0	1	1	0
6,18 – 6,52	0	1	1	1
6,52 – 6,86	1	0	0	0
6,86 – 7,20	1	0	0	1
7,20 – 7,54	1	0	1	0
7,54 – 7,88	1	0	1	1
7,88 – 8,22	1	1	0	0
8,22 – 8,56	1	1	0	1
8,56 – 8,90	1	1	1	0
> 8,90	1	1	1	1

Table 3: Relation between input voltages and digital outputs.

Better Analyzing the graphs on Fig. 5, it is possible to notice that there are certain voltage peaks, called ripple, in which, due to the intrinsic characteristics of the component, they appear several times in all the “digital outputs”. In order to remove them, a filter can be used at the output of each OR gates, thus eliminating the frequencies that generate by these ripples.

REFERENCES

- [1] FETTER, Gustavo da Cás et al. Desenvolvimento de conversor A/D com topologia paralela. 2015.
- [2] TOCCI, Ronald J.; WIDMER, Neal S.; MOSS, Gregory L. Sistemas digitais. Pearson Educación, 2010.
- [3] WALDEN, Robert H. Analog-to-digital converter survey and analysis. IEEE Journal on selected areas in communications, v. 17, n. 4, p. 539-550, 1999.
- [4] GULATI, Kush; LEE, Hae-Seung. A low-power reconfigurable analog-to-digital converter. IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits, v. 36, n. 12, p. 1900-1911, 2001.
- [5] Analog Devices. Understanding Flash ADCs. Disponível em: <https://www.analog.com/en/technical-articles/understanding-flash-adcs.html>. Acesso em: 27 abr. 2023.